

A Comparative Study to Gauge Emotional Hiccups among Adolescents

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ABSTRACT

The focus of this research study is to find the relation between various personality traits of adolescents based on the individual difference in their attitudes towards emotional affairs. In this paper, we have conceded the theoretical perspectives and available evidences about the influence of assertiveness, inferiority complex, emotional instability, self-control, tolerance, sense of well being, self-esteem, sense of personal worth, adaptability and sensitivity variables. Furthermore, the research has used data from adolescent boys and girls using questionnaire method (Personality Inventory For Adolescents - Anitha . S, Jayan. C) And appropriate statistical analysis – t test. The final result of the study suggests that there is significant difference in personality traits among girls and boys based on their relationship status.

Keywords: *Emotional Affairs, Assertiveness, Inferiority Complex, Emotional Instability, Self-Control, Tolerance, Sense of Well Being, Self-Esteem, Sense of Personal Worth, Adaptability, Sensitivity.*

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INTRODUCTION

Love in this age of big data - Many researchers, practitioners and la people alike believe that personality influences whether individuals lead a satisfying emotional affair. A growing body of research suggest that individual's predisposed personality traits has consequences in having a single relationship, adjourn or no engrossment in emotional affairs.

In this paper, we review theoretical perspectives and available evidence about the influences of 11 sub-variables of personality i.e., assertiveness, inferiority complex, emotional instability, self-control, tolerance, sense of well being, self-esteem, sense of personal worth, adaptability and sensitivity on adolescent boys and girls based on the individual difference in their attitudes towards emotional affairs. Adolescents boys and girls (N=60) completed the personality inventory for adolescents and a separate statistical analysis of t-test was employed. The results suggest certain significant differences in this aspect of study. Let us now briefly describe the relationship between the personality traits and emotional affairs.

Love has given humankind meaning and pleasure (as well as pain) for millennia. Human beings have taken different individual approaches to find a satisfactory emotional affair. For some it is a constant painful process and prefer in having no relation while others find it as a primary need to be with a significant other as a companion for life. An emotional affair is an emotional connection between two people which is emotionally provocative and intimate, hence susceptible to various personality traits.

Assertiveness is the ability to express their needs, wishes and feelings frankly, honestly and directly. Being assertive is about effective communication that helps to render good relationships; Inferiority complex is a psychological condition that exists when a

person's feelings of inadequacy are so intense that daily living is impaired. persistent worries or over excited emotions can hinder the emotional bond; Emotional instability refer to the state of qualities of being instable or unsteady in handling the emotional dealings and is one of the core reason for why many relationships break apart . Self control is the ability to manage anxiety and having the quality will get other people to value you more , it is the tone for most relationships; Tolerance is the quality of being able or willing to accept the behavior of others and in relationships it is less about your own needs and more about your partner's; Sense of Well being is the presence of positive marker characteristics that come about as a result chance combinations of organism, familial, community and social elements, and we cultivate relationships for this purpose; Self-Esteem is the feeling of being loved and accepted by others and a sense of competence and mastery in performing tasks and solving problems independently. There is an evident link between good self-esteem and satisfactory relationships; Sense of personal worth is the sense or feeling of being the same person, based mainly on common sensibility and continuity of aims, purposes and memories. Poor self wroth is what traps us in bad relationships; Social Skills is the ability for adaptive and positive behavior that enables individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday. Building good relationships is an outcome of good communication skills both verbally and non-verbally; Adaptability is the ability to make appropriate responses to changing circumstances. It directly relates to the degree of good satisfactory relationships; Sensitivity includes tender minded, independent, overprotected and insecurity. It can have adverse affects on the living of the individual if it alters the performance.

Carl E Pickhardt (2012) in his article 'Adolescence and falling in love' , have noted that when teenagers fall in love , what have they fallen into is a depth of caring more complex and compelling than they have known before. Adolescent romantic relationships- with all their ups and downs – have capacity to be growth – promoting, confidence-boosting and

healthy experiences that teach young people about the give and take of intimacy (Susan Moore). Winifred Gallagher (2001, The New York Times) mentioned about the Young Love: The Good, the Bad and the Educational.

In general i expect that there will be significant difference in some aspect of personality traits between the three groups under consideration i.e., people who has experienced an emotional breakup, no emotional breakup and having no relation.

METHOD

AIM

The aim of the study was to compare the personality traits of adolescent boys and girls based on their relationship status.

OBJECTIVES

The specific objectives of the study were as follows:

- a) To study the difference in personality traits among girls and boys based on relationship status.
- b) To study the difference in personality traits among girls and boys having experienced an emotional affair breakup.
- c) To study the difference in personality traits among girls and boys having not experienced an emotional affair breakup.
- d) To study the difference in personality traits among girls and boys having no emotional affair relation.

HYPOTHESES

1. There will be no significant difference in personality traits among girls and boys based on relationship status
2. There will be no significant difference in personality traits among girls and boys having experienced an emotional affair breakup.
3. There will be no significant difference in personality traits among girls and boys having not experienced an emotional affair breakup.
4. There will be no significant difference in personality traits among girls and boys having no emotional affair relation.

SAMPLE

60 adolescents agreed to participate in the study in which all of them were able to successfully complete the assessment and the final sample consisted of 30 girls and 30 boys . Group 1 consisted of 10 boys and 10 girls respectively who have experienced a emotional affair breakup. Group 2 consisted of 10 boys and 10 girls respectively who have not experienced a emotional affair breakup. Group 3 consisted of 10 boys and 10 girls who have no emotional affair relation. This agreed to the initially proposed sample size of 60 i.e., 10 in each group. The age group was comprised of adolescents of age between 18-21 yrs that was initially fixed. The sample was drawn from colleges Prajyoti Niketan College, St. Aloysius College and Vidya engineering college.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- a) Adolescent boys and girls having experienced an emotional breakup, who have not experienced an emotional breakup and having no relation.
- b) Age group; 18-21yrs

- c) Ability to read any one of the two languages; Malayalam or English.
- d) Individual's pursuing any educational course.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- a) Individuals who were doubtless about their relationship status.
- b) Individuals who were not interested to share their personal details.
- c) Individuals having major illness (Cancer)
- d) Individuals who were physically dependent on others for the day to day chores.
- e) Individuals with major psychosis such as (Schizophrenia), mental retardation and organic brain disorder.

PROCEDURE

Individuals of either sex belonging to any one of the three groups were asked permission to share their personal details about relationship status. They were further screened with the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and included in the study on the basis of convenient sampling. The purpose of the study was explained to them and informed to them and consent was taken. All individuals were individually seen and the study was carried out in a single phase.

The study period spread over a period of 3 weeks from September to October 2017. The administration was carried out in the absence of the experimenter. All measures were self reported. Doubts regarding specific items were clarified and complex items were explained in simple language.

LIST OF TOOLS

Personality Inventory for Adolescents

DESCRIPTION OF TOOLS

PERSONALITY INVENTORY FOR ADOLESCENTS

The scale was developed by S. Anitha and Dr. C. Jayan, consisting of 11 sub variables with 132 items. The scale consists of variables – Assertiveness (12 items, reliability= 0.82), Inferiority Complex (12 items, reliability= 0.71), Emotional Instability (12 items, reliability= 0.83), Self Control (12 items, reliability=0.73), Tolerance (12 items, reliability=0.94), Sense of Well Being (12 items, reliability=0.83), Self Esteem (12 items, reliability=0.92), Sense of Personal Worth (12 items, reliability=0.87), Social Skills (12 items, reliability= 0.71), Adaptability (12 items, reliability= 0.95) and Sensitivity (12 items, reliability=0.84). Patients were asked to rate the items with confidence on a 5-point Likert Scale (A=Strongly Agree, B=Agree, C=Undecided, D=Disagree, E=Strongly Disagree). Patient could not leave an item blank. The scales were moderately correlated with each other.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Statistical Package For Social Sciences (SPSS) – 16.0 Version was used to carry out the statistical analysis. Statistical analysis including independent student's t-test and Analysis Of Variance (ANOVA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study attempted to explore the difference in personality traits among girls and boys based on their relation status. Three independent samples, which differed on the basis of relationship status, were compared for the same. Personality sub variables – Assertiveness, Inferiority Complex, Emotional Instability, Self-Control, Tolerance, Sense of Well Being, Self-Esteem, Sense of Personal Worth, Adaptability and Sensitivity were compared to get

more information based on relationship status. There are not much systematic studies which had specifically looked into the parameters of relationship status.

SOCIO DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

The three groups in the study included individuals based on relationship status. Group 1 (n=20) included adolescent boys and girls having experienced an emotional breakup. Group 2 (n=20) included adolescent boys and girls having experienced no emotional breakup. Group 3 (n=20) included adolescent boys and girls having experienced no relation. In all three groups, level of education ranged from primary to college education. The age range of the obtained sample was 18-21 yrs. The sample comprises of 30 boys and 30 girls.

PROJECT FINDINGS

In the present study the association of personality traits between boys and girls was examined. A significant difference was obtained (Table 1).

Boys and girls were analyzed based on the personality traits. A significant difference in inferiority complex, emotional instability, self control, self esteem, social skills and adaptability were observed. The state of being happy, healthy or prosperous i.e., well being was found in a good satisfactory condition in females. It was found that woman has a sense of own value or worth as a person as compared with men. The scores of inferiority complex and social skills were contradictory to the expectation as it was more in males in the former and in females for the latter.

Table 1

Mean, S. D. and t-values of personality traits among girls and boys based on relationship status

Variables	Male (N=30)		Female (N=30)		t value
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	
Assertiveness	39.07	4.638	38.13	3.928	0.841
Inferiority Complex	34.00	10.171	20.60	5.787	6.272***
Emotional Instability	35.40	9.335	31.10	6.255	2.096*
Self Control	36.37	7.985	40.47	6.135	2.230*
Tolerance	32.40	8.156	34.73	7.656	1.142
Sense of Well Being	39.07	8.407	46.30	7.557	3.505
Self Esteem	36.43	6.479	41.57	6.663	3.025**
Sense of personal worth	38.87	7.833	44.97	5.846	3.418
Social Skills	40.33	7.053	47.43	6.202	4.14***1
Adaptability	39.83	5.213	46.23	4.216	5.229***
Sensitivity	40.97	6.916	40.97	5.340	0.000

*p<0.05 **p<0.01 ***p<0.001

Personality traits as a influence in adolescent boys and girls based on their relationship status was analyzed using Analysis Of Variance (ANOVA). There was no significant difference which was incongruent to the initial expectation. This is strikingly inconsistent with various articles. (Table 3, 4).

Table 2

Results of personality variables for groups based on emotional affairs

Variables	Break up (N=20)		No Break up (N=20)		No relation (N=20)	
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D

Assertiveness	38030	3.757	38.97	5.186	38.55	3.980
Inferiority Complex	27.65	10.205	26.75	11.670	27.50	10.486
Emotional Instability	35.35	8.273	33.15	9.086	31.25	6.889
Self Control	39.55	7.640	38.95	7.870	36.75	6.568
Tolerance	32.30	8.253	34.10	9.369	34.30	6.071
Sense of Well Being	42.55	8.003	41.50	10.665	44.00	7.435
Self Esteem	38.50	7.619	38.95	7.480	39.55	6.168
Sense of personal worth	41.60	8.623	41.95	8.211	42.20	5.764
Social Skills	44.30	8.014	43.50	9.064	43.85	5.264
Adaptability	42.60	5.041	42.85	7.184	43.65	4.826
Sensitivity	40.10	6.601	41.55	7.265	41.25	4.351

*p<0.05 **p<0.01 ***p<0.001

Table 3

Analysis of Variance of personality variables for groups based on relationship status

Variables	Between groups		Within groups		F - value
	Sum of squares	Mean square	Sum of squares	Mean square	
Assertiveness	4.300	2.150	1080.100	18.949	0.113
Inferiority Complex	9.300	4.650	6655.300	116.760	0.040
Emotional Instability	168.400	84.200	3770.850	66.155	1.273
Self Control	86.933	43.467	3105.650	54.485	0.798
Tolerance	48.533	24.267	3662.200	64.249	0.378

Sense of Well Being	63.033	31.517	4427.950	77.683	0.406
Self Esteem	11.100	5.550	2888.900	50.682	0.110
Sense of personal worth	3.633	1.817	3324.950	58.332	0.031
Social Skills	6.433	3.217	3307.750	58.031	0.55
Adaptability	12.033	6.017	1905.900	33.437	0.180
Sensitivity	23.433	11.717	2190.500	38.430	0.305

*p<0.05 **p<0.01 ***p<0.001

In the present study a significant difference was observed in the values of personality traits of boys and girls having emotional breakup in inferiority complex and adaptability. It was found that rapid, often, exaggerated changes in mood with strong emotions and feelings were seen more in male i.e., assorting them to be emotionally instable, probably in the light of prior experience of a breakup. (Table 4)

Table 4

Mean, S. D. and t-values of personality traits among girls and boys having emotional breakup

Variables	Male (N=10)		Female (N=10)		t value
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	
Assertiveness	38.30	4.547	38.30	3.020	0.000
Inferiority Complex	35.70	8.084	19.60	3.239	5.846***
Emotional Instability	38.70	9.429	32.00	5.538	1.938
Self Control	37.90	9.433	41.20	5.308	0.964
Tolerance	33.80	9.343	30.80	7.177	0.805

Sense of Well Being	39.90	8.346	45.20	7.068	1.532
Self Esteem	36.00	7.165	41.00	7.572	1.517
Sense of personal worth	37.80	10.152	45.40	4.671	2.151*
Social Skills	40.00	6.307	48.60	7.397	2.798
Adaptability	38.90	3.035	46.30	3.743	4.856***
Sensitivity	40.00	8.340	40.20	4.733	0.066

*p<0.05 **p<0.01 ***p<0.001

In the present study a significant difference was observed in the values of personality traits of boys and girls having no emotional breakup in inferiority complex. It were seen that females showed comparatively higher rates of self-esteem showing an ability to have an authentic, reciprocal relationship (Table5). It is evident that the low sense of personal worth is what cause individuals to fell so devastated and broken when a relationship ends. However, it is contradictory in the case of individuals with no emotional break up, which is satisfied in this study. Good relationships depend on the ability to adapt and the results indicate that woman shows more adaptive skills.

Table 5

Mean, S. D. and t-values of personality traits among girls and boys having no emotional break up

Variables	Male (N=10)		Female (N=10)		t value
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	
Assertiveness	39.50	5.817	38.40	4.719	0.464
Inferiority Complex	35.00	10.414	18.50	5.276	4.470***

Emotional Instability	35.10	11.180	31.20	6.391	0.958
Self Control	37.30	8.274	40.60	7.501	0.934
Tolerance	31.40	9.216	36.80	9.175	1.313
Sense of Well Being	37.50	10.554	45.50	9.652	1.769
Self Esteem	34.70	6.360	43.20	6.125	3.044**
Sense of personal worth	37.30	7.528	46.60	6.132	3.029**
Social Skills	39.80	9.739	47.20	6.941	1.957
Adaptability	39.30	7.212	46.40	5.379	2.496*
Sensitivity	41.90	7.866	41.20	7.021	0.210

*p<0.05 **p<0.01 ***p<0.001

Personality traits of adolescent boys and girls having no relation found a significant difference in well being, self control, social skills and adaptability. The individuals condition is positive from the perspective of individuals interested primarily in the mental health domain.

Table 6*Mean, S. D. and t-values of personality traits among girls and boys having no relation*

Variables	Male (N=10)		Female (N=10)		t value
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	
Assertiveness	39.40	3.718	37.70	4.244	0.953
Inferiority Complex	31.30	12.129	23.70	7.273	1.699
Emotional Instability	32.40	6.687	30.10	7.249	0.738
Self Control	33.90	6.136	39.60	5.948	2.109*
Tolerance	32.00	6.218	36.60	5.232	1.790
Sense of Well Being	39.80	6.529	48.20	5.903	3.018**
Self Esteem	38.60	5.892	40.50	6.604	0.679
Sense of personal worth	41.50	5.126	42.90	6.540	0.533
Social Skills	41.20	4.940	46.50	4.301	2.599*
Adaptability	41.30	4.762	46.00	3.771	2.447*
Sensitivity	41.00	4.546	41.50	4.378	0.251

*p<0.05 **p<0.01 ***p<0.001

On the whole the study indicated significant difference in certain aspects of personality traits based on the relationship status. It is evident that the prolongation of the relationship or the time rendered in emotional affairs becomes a more prominent factor.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The present study was aimed at exploring the personality traits of adolescent boys and girls based on their relationship status.

The main objectives of the study were

- a) To study the difference in personality traits among girls and boys based relationship status.
- b) To study the difference in personality traits among girls and boys having experienced an emotional affair breakup.
- c) To study the difference in personality traits among girls and boys having not experienced an emotional affair breakup.
- d) To study the difference in personality traits among girls and boys having no emotional affair relation.

In view of the above objective the following hypotheses were proposed:

- a) There will be no significant difference in personality traits among girls and boys based on relationship status..
- b) There will be no significant difference in personality traits among girls and boys having experienced an emotional affair breakup.
- c) There will be no significant difference in personality traits among girls and boys having not experienced an emotional affair breakup.
- d) There will be no significant difference in personality traits among girls and boys having no emotional affair relation.

Tools appropriate for the study was selected to measure the relevant variables and translated version of the selected tools were also used. All the tools were self rated. Clarifications were done by the examiner, regarding the difficult items.

The final sample comprised of 60 individuals with 20 in Group 1, 20 in Group 2 and 20 in Group 3 respectively. Group 1 included individuals having experienced an emotional affair breakup, Group 2 included individuals having experienced no emotional affair breakup and Group 3 included individuals having experienced no emotional affair relation. The sample was drawn from students of Prajyoti Niketan College, St. Aloysius College and Vidya Engineering College. The age range of the sample was 18-21 yrs. The sample comprises of 30 boys and 30 girls. Out of 60, 20 were in Group 1, 20 in Group 2 and 20 in Group 3. All of them were college students and invariably have primary education as it being one of the inclusion criteria.

Personal Inventory tool For Adolescents were used. Data was collected within a time period of 3 weeks. Data was treated with statistical analyses including, independent students t- test and ANOVA, using statistical package for social sciences- version 16.

CONCLUSION

- a) Boys and girls were significantly different in the personality traits.
- b) There is significant difference in personality traits; inferiority complex, adaptability among boys and girls having emotional breakup.
- c) There is significant difference in the personality traits: inferiority complex among boys and girls having no emotional affair.
- d) There is significant difference in the personality traits: well- being, self control, sense of personal worth and social skills among boys and girls having no emotional relation.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- a) In the present study there was no attempt to include individuals who have no relation even though have a prior experience of breakup.
- b) The present study had an under representation of female sample.
- c) The present study has followed a convenience sampling technique.
- d) Major life events which might cause potential changes in both negative and positive direction during the study period have not been controlled
- e) Changes in socio- economic status were not studied.

FUTURE SUGGESTIONS

- a) The study can be improvised by including individuals who have no relation even though have a prior experience of breakup.
- b) More reliable Tools measuring different aspects can be included.
- c) The duration of study period can be extended to more than one year.
- d) Attempt can be made to control at least some of the major risk factors.

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